

Clinico-Epidemiological Profile of HIV Reactive Clients in the HIV Counselling and Testing Centre (HCTC) at Rural Tertiary Care Teaching Hospital

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Abstract:

Objective: To determine the epidemiological profile of HIV reactive clients. To identify the type of risky behaviour responsible for the transmission of HIV/AIDS.

Material and Methods: A retrospective cross-sectional study was conducted using clinical records of clients registered at HIV Counselling and Testing Centre (HCTC) at C. U. Shah Medical College and Hospital, Surendranagar, Gujarat from January 2021 to June 2023. The data was processed and analysed in Microsoft excel.

Results: Out of total 98 HIV reactive clients, 79 were males, 18 were females while only 1 was transgender. Out of 79 male HIV reactive male clients, majority (17 in no.) were in the age group of 36-45 years. Out of 18 HIV reactive female clients, majority (5 in no.) were in the age group of 26-35 and 36-45 years. Transgender was in the age group of 16-25 years. 63.29% male and 66.66% female HIV reactive clients were married. 40.5% male were on daily wages as occupation and 44.44% female were housewives. Majority of HIV reactive client i.e., 97.95% were having heterosexual relation as a type of risky behavior responsible for the transmission.

Conclusion: The epidemiological studies must be conducted in the various centres to understand the demographic factors which helps the policy makers to take appropriate and necessary interventions to interrupt and control the transmission of HIV/AIDS.

Keywords: HIV Reactive Clients, Epidemiological Profile.

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Introduction

Human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) was recognized in early 1980s, since then it had brought about the physical, emotional and social devastation in the world. The population affected by this virus has increased tremendously across the world [1]. According to the UNAIDS/WHO Estimates (2023), the people living with HIV/AIDS (PLHA) in world are 39 million [2]. According to India HIV Estimates 2021 fact sheet by NACO & ICMR, PLHA in India and Gujarat are 24.01 and 1.13 Lakh respectively [3]. The HIV Counselling and Testing Centre (HCTC) acts a centre for care and opportunity to accept the HIV sero-status in a smooth and confidential manner. The data collected from HCTC helps to implement the effective approach to control and prevent the disease by better understanding of the epidemiology in the particular region [4]. Therefore, this study is directed towards

the determination of epidemiological profile of HIV reactive clients.

Objective

- To determine the epidemiological profile of HIV reactive clients.
- To identify risk behaviour among HIV reactive clients.

Material and Methods

A retrospective cross-sectional study was conducted using records of clients registered at HIV Counselling and Testing Centre (HCTC) at C. U. Shah Medical College and Hospital, Surendranagar, Gujarat from January 2021 to June 2023. The data was processed and analysed in Microsoft excel. A total 98 clients were registered HIV reactive at HCTC. The ethical approval for this study was obtained

from Institutional Ethical Committee and Gujarat State AIDS Control Society.

Results

Chart 1: Age and gender wise distribution of HIV reactive status

Out of total 98 HIV reactive clients, 79 were males, 18 were females while only 1 was transgender.

Out of 79 HIV reactive male clients, 15 clients belong to the age group of 16-25 years, 22 clients belong to the age group of 26-35 years, 17 clients belong to the age group of 36-45 years, 15 clients belong to the age group of 46-55 years while 10 clients belong to the age group of 56-65 years. Out of 18 HIV reactive female clients, 1 client belong

to the age group of <5 years, 2 clients belong to the age group of 16-25 years, 5 clients belong to the age group of 26-35 years, 5 clients belong to the age group of 36-45 years, 4 clients belong to the age group of 46-55 years while 1 client belong to the age group of 56-65 years. Only 1 client in the age group of 16-25 years belong to transgender.

The median age group of the HIV reactive clients were 26-35 years.

Table 1: Distribution by marital status

Marital status	Male No. (%)	Female No. (%)
Married	50 (63.29%)	12 (66.66%)
Single	19 (24.05%)	1 (5.55%)
Divorcee/ separate	4 (5.06%)	0 (0%)
Widowed	6 (7.59%)	5 (27.77%)
Total	79 (80.61%)	18 (18.36%)

The distribution by the marital status shows out of 79 male HIV reactive clients, 63.29% were married, followed by 24.05% single, 7.59% widowed and 5.06% divorcee/separate. Out of 18 female HIV reactive clients, 66.66% were married, followed by 27.77% widowed and 5.55% single. While only 1 transgender HIV reactive client was single.

Table 2: Education wise distribution

Level of education	Male No. (%)	Female No. (%)	Transgender No. (%)
Illiterate/ Just literate	23 (29.11%)	13 (72.22%)	0 (0%)
Primary	36 (45.56%)	4 (22.22%)	1 (100%)
Secondary	14 (17.72%)	1 (5.55%)	0 (0%)
Graduate and above	6 (7.59%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)

The distribution by the level of education shows out of 79 male HIV reactive clients, 29.11% were illiterate while 45.56% were educated till primary level followed by 17.72% till secondary level while

only 7.59% were graduated. Out of 18 female HIV reactive clients, 72.22% were illiterate while 22.22% were educated till primary level followed by 5.55% till secondary level. The single transgender client was educated till primary level.

Table 3: Occupation wise distribution

Occupation	Male No. (%)	Female No.(%)
Daily wages	32 (40.50%)	3 (16.66%)
Salaried	16 (20.25%)	6 (33.33%)
Business	1 (1.26%)	0 (0%)
Housewife	0 (0%)	8 (44.44%)
Retired	5 (6.32%)	0 (0%)
Driver	6 (7.59%)	0 (0%)
Others	19 (24.05%)	1 (5.55%)

The distribution by occupation shows out of 79 male HIV reactive clients, 40.50% were in group of daily wages, 20.25% were involved in salaried job, 1.26% were involved in business, 6.32% were retired, 7.59% were drivers and 24.05% were involved in other occupation which were not men-

tioned. Out of 18 female HIV reactive clients, 16.66% were in group of daily wages, 33.33% were involved in salaried job, 44.44% were housewife, 5.55% were involved in other occupation. The single transgender client was involved in other occupation.

Chart 2: Distribution according to type of risky behaviour

The distribution according to the pattern of risky behaviour and reactive status, 98% are involved in heterosexual relations while only 1% involved in homosexual relation and parent to child transmission.

Discussion

Table 4: Age and gender wise HIV reactive status

Age	Gender	Present	Kiran et al.
26- 35 years	Male	27.84%	22.73%
	Female	27.77%	22.86%
36-45 years	Male	21.51%	34.85%
	Female	27.77%	34.29%

As per present study, 27.84% HIV reactive male client belongs to age group of 26-35 years followed by 21.51% belonging to age group of 36-45 years, while study by Kiran A. et al. shows 22.73% HIV reactive male clients in the age group of 26-35 years and 34.85% in the age group of 36-45 years.

In present study, 27.77% HIV reactive female client belongs to age group of 26-35 years and 36-45 years, while study by Kiran A. et al. shows 22.86% HIV reactive female clients in the age group of 26-35 years and 34.29% in the age group of 36-45 years [5].

Table 5: Distribution by marital status

Marital status	Present	Kommula V. et al.
Married male	63.29%	86.10%
Married female	66.66%	64.70%
Single male	24.05%	8.50%
Widowed female	27.77%	20.30%

As per present study, 63.29% HIV reactive male clients were married while study by Kommula V. et al. shows different result as 86.1% male were married. Similar result was shown in case of HIV reactive females as 66.66% and 64.7% were married

in present and Kommula V. et al. study respectively. Almost similar results were shown in case of widowed HIV reactive female in present and Kommula V. et al. study as 27.77% and 20.3% respectively [6].

Table 6: Education wise distribution

Level of education	HIV reactive Client	Present	Kommula V. et al.
Illiterate/ Just literate	Male	29.11%	48.40%
	Female	72.22%	61.10%
Primary	Male	45.56%	26.30%
	Female	22.20%	22.70%

As per present study, 29.11% HIV reactive male clients were illiterate/ just literate while study by Kommula V. et al. shows different result as 48.4% male were illiterate/ just literate. Similar result was shown in case of HIV reactive females as 72.22% and 61.1% were illiterate/ just literate in present and Kommula V. et al. study respectively. Different results were shown in case of HIV reactive male as 45.56% and 26.3% were educated till primary

level in present and Kommula V. et al. study respectively. Almost similar results were shown in case of HIV reactive female who were educated till primary level in present and Kommula V. et al. study as 27.20% and 22.7% respectively [6]. The rate of transmission among the literate people are more than the illiterate, the level of education did not play any role in prevention of transmission of the disease.

Table 7: Occupation wise distribution

	Occupation	Present	Kommula V. et al.
Male	Daily wages	40.50%	21.70%
	Other occupation as such driver	31.64%	8.50%
Female	Housewife	44.44%	40.70%
	Salaried	33.33%	5.93%

The different results were shown in the case of occupation wise distribution in present and study by Kommula V. et al. expect in HIV reactive female who were housewives as 44.44% and 40.7% respectively [6].

Table 8: Distribution according to type of risky behaviour

Type of risky behaviour	Present	Kommula V. et al.
Heterosexual	97.95%	83.70%
Homosexual	1.02%	1.30%
Parent to child	1.02%	4%

As per present study, 97.95% were involved in heterosexual relation and almost similar results were shown in study by Kommula V. et al. as 83.7% [6].

Conclusion

The trend of HIV/AIDS depends upon the epidemiological profile and risk behaviour of HIV reactive clients in the particular area. Hence, the epidemiological studies must be conducted in the various centres to understand the demographic factors which helps the policy makers to take appro-

priate and necessary interventions to interrupt and control the transmission of HIV/AIDS. The various studies at regular interval of time helps to find the change in pattern of trends in transmission of HIV/AIDS.

Recommendation

From the present study, the Heterosexual route

of transmission is more than other modes so, it can be reduced by education/ awareness about the disease and the use of barrier contraceptives. The rate of transmission in the literate people can be reduced by the proper education about the sexually transmitted diseases and its prevention in the school and colleges.

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